

SITTING LOUNGE
DESIGN

NISHAT BOUTIQUE
HOTEL

ARCH REF. IMAGE

LAMP REF. IMAGE

LAMP REF. IMAGE

LAMP REF. IMAGE

KEY PLAN

CDM RESIDUAL RISKS

THIS DRAWING HAS BEEN REVIEWED AGAINST THE DESIGN CDM ROLLING RISK REGISTER AND KNOWN SIGNIFICANT RESIDUAL RISKS HAVE BEEN IDENTIFIED.

CONSTRUCTION		 SIGNIFICANT HAZARD REF
MAINTENANCE/CLEANING		
DECOMMISSIONING/DEMOLITION		

NOTES

ARRIS CONSULTANTS

client name	NISHAT BOUTIQUE HOTEL	
project	SITTING LOUNGE	
drawing	REF. IMAGES	
computer file	plot date	02-28-24
project number	scale	
drawing number	rev	issue status
INT-001	00	

This drawing is to be read in conjunction with all related drawings. Do not scale from this drawing. All dimensions must be checked and verified on site before commencing any work or producing shop drawings. The originator should be notified immediately of any discrepancy. This drawing is copyright and remains the property of ARRIS Consultants.

LAMP REF. IMAGE

CHAIR REF. IMAGE

COFFEE TABLE REF. IMAGE

SOFA REF. IMAGE

KEY PLAN

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CONSTRUCTION		 SIGNIFICANT HAZARD REF
MAINTENANCE/CLEANING		
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NOTES

ARRIS CONSULTANTS

client name	NISHAT BOUTIQUE HOTEL	
project	SITTING LOUNGE	

REF. IMAGES

computer file	plot date	02-28-24
project number	scale	
drawing number	rev	00
INT-001	issue status	

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MAINTENANCE/CLEANING		
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NOTES

ARRIS CONSULTANTS

client name	NISHAT BOUTIQUE HOTEL
project	SITTING LOUNGE
drawing	LAYOUT PLAN

computer file	plot date	02-28-24
project number	scale	
drawing number	rev	00
INT-001	issue status	

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MAINTENANCE/CLEANING		
DECOMMISSIONING/DEMOLITION		

NOTES

ELEVATION - 01
SITTING LOUNGE

ARRIS CONSULTANTS

client name	NISHAT BOUTIQUE HOTEL		
project	SITTING LOUNGE		
drawing	ELEVATION-01		
computer file	plot date	02-28-24	
project number	scale		
drawing number	rev	issue status	
INT-002	00		

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NOTES

ELEVATION - 02
SITTING LOUNGE

ARRIS CONSULTANTS

client name	NISHAT BOUTIQUE HOTEL		
project	SITTING LOUNGE		
drawing	ELEVATION-02		
computer file	plot date	02-28-24	
project number	scale		
drawing number	rev	issue status	
INT-003	00		

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NOTES

ELEVATION - 03
SITTING LOUNGE

ARRIS CONSULTANTS

client name	NISHAT BOUTIQUE HOTEL	
project	SITTING LOUNGE	
drawing	ELEVATION-03	
computer file	plot date	02-28-24
project number	scale	
drawing number	rev	issue status
INT-004	00	

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NOTES

ELEVATION - 04
SITTING LOUNGE

ARRIS CONSULTANTS

client name	NISHAT BOUTIQUE HOTEL	
project	SITTING LOUNGE	
drawing	ELEVATION-04	
computer file	plot date	02-28-24
project number	scale	
drawing number	rev	issue status
INT-005	00	

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